

Systematic errors in strong lensing models of galaxy clusters : Implications for cosmography

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A long standing issue of modern cosmology

Better **understand** the constituents of the Universe
(**nature and properties**)

Placing **better constraints** on some **cosmological parameters**

Combination of several cosmological probes used to derive cosmological parameters :

CMB, SNIa, BAO, WL
&
STRONG LENSING

Strong Lensing : a powerful tool

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$$\alpha = \frac{D_{LS}}{D_{OS}} \nabla \varphi(\theta_1)$$

SL is sensitive to the total cluster mass
(baryons + dark matter)

Jauzac et al. 2014
MACS0416

Cosmography method : a geometrical probe

SL has already proven to be a **very effective tool** to recover the cosmology similar to other cosmological probes

Jullo et al., 2010; D'Aloisio & Natarajan, 2011

$$\alpha = \frac{D_{LS}}{D_{OS}} \nabla \varphi(\theta_1)$$

cosmology

mass

Jullo et al. 2010

G. B. Caminha et al. 2015

HST Frontier Fields

Abell 2744

MACS J0416.1-2403

MACS J0717.5+3745

MACS J1149.5+2223

Abell S1063

Abell 370

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840 orbits dedicated to the observation of 6
strong lensing clusters

HST Frontier Fields

* 10-100 times fainter background sources

Cluster mass reconstructions are much more precise!

* Hundreds of multiple images, covering a broad redshift range

Mahler et al. 2017, Abell 2744

Limousin et al. 2016, MACS 0717

Lagattuta et al. 2016, Abell 370

Sebesta et al. 2016, MACS 0416

Frontier Fields Comparison Project

Ares & Hera

Semi- Analytical « MOKA » model
(*Giocoli et al. 2012*)
242 images from 85 sources

N-body simulation
65 images from 19 sources

***See Meneghetti et al. 2016 for more info on the
Ares & Hera modelling***

Frontier Fields Comparison Project

Ares & Hera

See Meneghetti et al. 2016

Frontier Fields Comparison Project

Ares & Hera

LENSTOOL (Kneib et al. 1993; Jullo et al. 2007)

See Meneghetti et al. 2016

SL

modelling

GOAL : Recover an accurate mass distribution of cluster cores
+ magnification...

SL parametric modelling

GOAL : Recover an accurate mass distribution of cluster cores
+ magnification...

DM + Intra Cluster gas

+

BCGs

+

Galactic haloes

Ares & Hera modelling

Ares results

Model	log(Likelihood)	RMS(")	Reduced χ^2	log(Evidence)	BIC	AICc	Ω_M	w
PIEMD - no BCGs	76.61	1.80	1.27	33.51	-15.23	-24.44	$0.24^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	$-1.57^{+0.15}_{-0.23}$
PIEMD - PIEMD	117.00	0.66	0.81	61.46	-32.77	-37.93	$0.28^{+0.10}_{-0.06}$	$-1.02^{+0.05}_{-0.02}$
NFW - no BCGs	144.83	0.60	0.61	95.78	-163.17	-97.35	$0.31^{+0.06}_{-0.06}$	$-1.09^{+0.10}_{-0.24}$
NFW - PIEMD	155.28	0.73	0.58	100.70	-109.33	-83.76	$0.24^{+0.05}_{-0.05}$	$-1.03^{+0.06}_{-0.14}$
NFW - PIEMD + SUBS	166.53	0.55	0.48	107.65	-45.59	-47.14	$0.19^{+0.06}_{-0.03}$	$-0.99^{+0.05}_{-0.10}$
NFW - HERNQUIST	145.54	0.58	0.61	93.58	-118.59	-78.97	$0.27^{+0.03}_{-0.11}$	$-1.05^{+0.06}_{-0.27}$
NFW - HERNQUIST + SUBS	168.31	0.64	0.50	111.43	-60.65	-55.69	$0.33^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$	$-1.25^{+0.13}_{-0.12}$
NFW - PIEMD + shapes	135.56	0.57	0.65	79.82	-87.14	-64.04	$0.22^{+0.10}_{-0.05}$	$-0.90^{+0.07}_{-0.12}$

Hera results

Model	log(Likelihood)	RMS(")	Reduced χ^2	log(Evidence)	BIC	AICc	Ω_M	w
PIEMD - no BCGs	-35.93	0.99	2.85	-77.20	207.51	126.42	$0.54^{+0.14}_{-0.20}$	$-1.15^{+0.18}_{-0.73}$
PIEMD - PIEMD	-19.44	1.21	2.64	-64.97	210.71	151.36	$0.41^{+0.12}_{-0.09}$	$-1.55^{+0.58}_{-0.09}$
PIEMD - HERNQUIST	-31.80	0.96	2.98	-71.60	226.38	152.24	$0.44^{+0.16}_{-0.20}$	$-1.05^{+0.15}_{-0.57}$
NFW - no BCGs	-43.44	0.98	2.71	-79.81	222.53	133.93	$0.71^{+0.09}_{-0.30}$	$-1.30^{+0.64}_{-0.37}$
NFW - PIEMD	-46.47	1.00	3.03	-85.40	264.77	178.39	$0.33^{+0.18}_{-0.10}$	$-1.19^{+0.21}_{-0.50}$
NFW - HERNQUIST	-44.59	0.99	2.96	-81.40	251.96	165.02	$0.32^{+0.22}_{-0.07}$	$-1.48^{+0.47}_{-0.24}$

Quality assessment

1. Density profiles

- *All models (but PIEMD) recover well the mass distribution in the central regions
- *Inclusion of substructures improves the fit on the cluster's outskirts

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3. Relative bias on magnification

- * Bias of $\sim 20\%$ for *Ares* & $\sim 30\%$ for *Hera*, difficult to decrease
- * Precision on magnification measurements improves with increasing number of constraints

A quality indicator

The smaller the bias on the mass, the smaller the bias on cosmological parameters

Photometric redshifts complement

1. z_{phot} precision = $0.04(1+z)$
Castellano et al. 2016 for HFF

Reference (all z_{spec}) in black
 $Z_{\text{spec}} + Z_{\text{phot}}$ (precision=0.04)
Only Z_{spec}
True Value

Increasing the number of constraints with photometric redshifts decreases the bias on cosmological parameters

Photometric redshifts complement

1. zphot precision = **0.04**(1+z)
Castellano et al. 2016 for HFF

2. zphot precision = **0.02**(1+z)
Molino et al. 2017 for HST/CLASH

Photometric redshifts complement

Conclusions

- SL is a promising tool to constrain cosmological parameters...
- ... which can also be obtained with more complex and multimodal clusters !
- Distant & massive substructures can bias the results
- The smallest the error on the mass, the better the cosmological results
- w is more sensitive to systematic errors than Ω_M
- Photometric redshifts help decrease the bias on cosmological parameters

Acebron+17
arXiv: 1704.05380

What now ?

- Extend analysis to less « idealised » mock clusters
- Better understanding of cluster's outskirts
(structures and physical processes)
- Obtain cosmological constraints with REAL clusters
—▶ Frontier Fields !

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arXiv: 1704.05380

Thank you for your attention !

Underestimating the uncertainty on the observations can lead to biased results